

DAMAGE EVOLUTION MODELING IN MULTIDIRECTIONAL LAMINATES AND THE RESULTING NONLINEAR RESPONSE

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SUMMARY: Stiffness reduction in $[S,90_n]_s$ symmetric laminates, containing orthotropic sub-laminates (S) is analyzed as a function of crack density in 90^0 layer. Closed form expressions relating stiffness changes to the transverse crack density are used to compute stiffness changes due to accumulated damage. Weibull strength distribution of 90^0 layer is assumed and Shear Lag and Hashin's models are used for calculation of stress distribution in 90^0 layer with cracks. Weibull parameters are obtained from experimental data for $[0_2, 90_4]_s$ laminate and then used for other lay-ups. Strength approach and Monte-Carlo simulation is used to estimate damage evolution in 90^0 layer and crack density as a function of applied strain is obtained. It is used to predict stiffness changes in $[S,90_n]_s$ laminates as a function of applied strain. Predictions are compared with experimental data for $[\pm\theta, 90_4]_s$ $\theta= 0,15,30,40$ GF/EP laminates. Comparison shows fairly good agreement between prediction and experimental.

KEYWORDS: laminates, damage evolution, stiffness reduction, Weibull distribution, transverse cracking, Monte-Carlo simulation.

INTRODUCTION

Cross-ply laminate, which contains layers oriented only in two directions - parallel and transverse to the loading direction, is one of the most commonly suggested for analysis and modeling of the elastic property changes. The first damage that occurs in those laminates is transverse cracking - formation of intra-laminar cracks running parallel to fibers in the 90^0 - layer due to fiber-matrix debonding and matrix cracking. Transverse cracking is a progressive damage that evolves with increase of the applied strain and the measure of the accumulated damage is crack density. Therefore, changes of elastic properties of laminate, such as longitudinal Young's modulus and major Poisson's ratio, are related to the number of cracks formed in the transverse layer. Number of studies was performed in order to predict degradation of properties of cross-ply laminates due to transverse cracking. These studies are based on different approaches; different modifications of the shear lag model [1] were one of the firsts and probably the most frequently used. Hashin [2] developed more accurate model based on variational approach - minimization of the complementary energy. These models use crack density as a given parameter, which is not the case in real situation. Usually applied strain is given and crack density is unknown. Therefore, from practical point of view, model that can predict stiffness reduction as a function of applied strain is more

preferable. One of the methods to estimate damage evolution is Monte-Carlo simulation of the cracking in 90^0 layer. In this case strength distribution of 90^0 layer is assumed to be Weibull distribution and stress in damaged layer is calculated by one of the mentioned models.

In this study it is assumed that the Weibull parameters of the strength distribution of the 90^0 layer are the same for all laminate lay-ups, since they contain the same middle layer. These parameters are obtained from one lay-up – cross ply laminate and then used for all other lay-ups to model multiple cracking. Strength approach is used: crack appears if stress in 90^0 layer exceeds strength. Damage evolution with increasing applied strain is obtained by Monte-Carlo simulation procedure. Expressions [3] for stiffness and Poisson's ratio reduction as a function of crack density are applied for laminates with simple $[\pm\theta/90_4]$ lay-up, where $\theta = 0,15,30,40$. Relationship between crack density and applied strain obtained from Monte-Carlo simulation is used to obtain stiffness reduction as a function of applied strain. Good agreement is obtained comparing predictions with experimental results.

EXPERIMENTAL

Toughened Glass Fiber (GF)/Epoxy (EP) prepreg was used to produce composite plates with lay-up $[\pm\theta/90_4]$, $\theta = 0,15,30,40$. Detailed description of curing cycle and specimen preparation can be found in [3].

Tensile test was carried out on INSTRON 1272 tensile machine with 25 kN load cell. The experiment was performed in displacement controlled mode with stroke rate 2 mm/min. During loading longitudinal displacement was measured by MTS extensometer, but in order to measure transverse strain, CEA-06-240UZ-120 strain gage was bonded to the specimen and connected to the quarter of the Wheatstone bridge. All output data were collected by the acquisition system and transmitted to the PC.

Step-by-step loading cycle was performed. Specimens were loaded till the level where new transverse cracks were formed. After each loading step specimen was unloaded till load level where cracking process stops, and cracks were counted by visual observation. Then specimen was further unloaded and reloaded several times in the stroke region where cracks are not formed. These data were used to obtain elastic constants. For all specimens longitudinal Young's modulus and Poisson's ratio were calculated in the same linear stress-strain curve region, in the axial strain interval 0.10-0.35%.

MODELING

Stiffness of laminate with cracks

Symmetric and balanced $[S, 90_n]_s$ laminate, consisting of two balanced sub-laminates as outer layers and 90^0 -layer in the middle, is studied. When such laminate is loaded in uniaxial tension the first damage which occurs is transverse cracking in the middle layer. The spacing between cracks can be assumed equidistant, which means that laminate contains a periodical array of cracks in 90^0 -layer. The geometry of the repeatable unit used for modeling is shown in Fig. 1. Dimensionless coordinates can be introduced:

$$\bar{z} = \frac{z}{d} \quad \bar{x} = \frac{x}{d} \quad \bar{l}_0 = \frac{l_0}{d} \quad \bar{b} = \frac{b}{d} \quad \bar{h} = \frac{h}{d} \quad (1)$$

Loading is applied only in x -direction and the far field applied stress is defined by $\sigma_0 = \frac{1}{2h} N_x$, where N_x is applied load.

Fig. 1: Schematic picture of the representative element of the laminate

It is shown [3] that stiffness and Poisson's ratio reduction as a function of crack density can be calculated by following closed form expressions:

$$\frac{E_x}{E_{x0}} = \frac{1}{1 + \frac{E_2 d (1 - \nu_{12} \nu_{xy}^0)}{E_x^s b (1 - \nu_{12} \nu_{21})} \frac{1}{2 \bar{l}_0} R(\bar{l}_0) \left(1 + \nu_{xy}^s \frac{(S_{xy}^s d + S_{12} b)}{(S_{yy}^s d + S_{11} b)} \right)} \quad (2)$$

$$\nu_{xy} = - \frac{-\nu_{xy}^0 + E_2 \frac{(1 - \nu_{12} \nu_{xy}^0)}{(1 - \nu_{12} \nu_{21})} \frac{d}{2 \bar{l}_0} R(\bar{l}_0) \frac{S_{xy}^s S_{11} - S_{12} S_{yy}^s}{S_{yy}^s d + S_{11} b}}{1 + \frac{E_2 d (1 - \nu_{12} \nu_{xy}^0)}{E_x^s b (1 - \nu_{12} \nu_{xy}^0)} \frac{1}{2 \bar{l}_0} R(\bar{l}_0) \left(1 - \frac{S_{xy}^s (S_{xy}^s d + S_{12} b)}{S_{xx}^s (S_{yy}^s d + S_{11} b)} \right)} \quad (3)$$

More details and explanations of the used notations are given in Appendix.

Expressions (2) and (3) contain elastic constants of the unidirectional composite and sub-laminate and laminate geometry. Those are either given or can be calculated by classical laminate theory. The only unknown is stress perturbation function $R(l_0)$. General expression for this function is following:

$$R(\bar{l}_0) = \int_{-\bar{l}_0}^{+\bar{l}_0} \psi(\bar{x}) d\bar{x} \quad (4)$$

Function $\psi(x)$ is related to perturbed stress in 90^0 layer with crack:

$$\sigma_x^{90} = \sigma_{x0}^{90} (1 - \psi(\bar{x})) \quad (5)$$

Far field stress in the middle layer is given by (see Appendix for notations):

$$\sigma_{x0}^{90} = \varepsilon_x E_2 \frac{E_x}{E_{x0}} \quad (6)$$

Function $\psi(x)$ can be approximately calculated by Shear Lag or Hashin's model. In this study three micromechanical models will be considered (see Appendix):

- shear lag model assuming resin rich layer on the 0^0 - 90^0 layer interface (Sh.L.-1);
- shear lag model assuming linear displacement distribution in 90^0 layer (Sh.L.-2);
- Hashin's variational model (Hashin's).

Therefore stress distribution in 90^0 layer can be obtained along the whole length of the laminate at any applied strain ϵ_x and any given crack spacing l_0 . This procedure is used in Monte-Carlo simulation, when applied strain is increased in small steps and stress distribution is calculated.

Strength distribution in 90^0 layer

Strength distribution in 90^0 layer is needed, since strength approach in damage evolution modeling is used. For brittle material strength distribution is given by two-parameter Weibull distribution:

$$P_s = \exp\left[-(\epsilon / \beta)^\alpha\right], \quad (7)$$

where P_s is probability of survival at a given stress, ϵ is strain, α – shape parameter and β is scale parameter. Probability density function of this distribution is obtained by derivation of Eqn. 7:

$$f(\epsilon) = \epsilon^{\alpha-1} \frac{\alpha}{\beta^\alpha} \exp\left[-(\epsilon / \beta)^\alpha\right] \quad (8)$$

Weibull parameters may be obtained from experimental data of cracking of cross-ply laminates by method developed by Peters and used by others [4]. In this study simulation of the whole damage evolution process including crack interaction at high crack density is done first. Then results corresponding to simulations with different Weibull parameters are compared with experiment. The best fit of computer simulated result to experiment gives Weibull parameters.

Discretisation of Weibull distribution

Specimen is considered as consisting of M elements. Strength of each element must be assigned according to Weibull strength distribution. In order to use Weibull distribution in computer simulation it should be converted from continuous to discretised form. The procedure is following:

1. Calculate average strength $\bar{\epsilon}$ and standard deviation s :

$$\bar{\epsilon} = \beta \Gamma\left(1 + \frac{1}{\alpha}\right) \quad s = \beta \sqrt{\Gamma\left(1 + \frac{2}{\alpha}\right) - \Gamma^2\left(1 + \frac{1}{\alpha}\right)}$$

2. Interval on which calculation will be performed is chosen $[\epsilon_{\min}, \epsilon_{\max}]$:

$$\epsilon_{\min} = \bar{\epsilon} - \kappa s \quad \epsilon_{\max} = \bar{\epsilon} + \kappa s, \text{ where } \kappa = \frac{\bar{\epsilon}}{s} \Rightarrow \epsilon_{\min} = 0, \epsilon_{\max} = 2\bar{\epsilon}.$$

3. Divide the complete interval in small intervals with length $\Delta\epsilon$:

$$\Delta\epsilon = \frac{\epsilon_{\max} - \epsilon_{\min}}{I}, \text{ where } I - \text{ number of intervals.}$$

4. Calculate average value of strain for each interval:

$$\epsilon_1 = \epsilon_{\min} + \Delta\epsilon / 2 \quad \epsilon_i = \epsilon_1 + i\Delta\epsilon, \quad i=2\dots I.$$

5. Calculate density function $f(\epsilon)$ in the *middle* of each interval: $f_i = f(\epsilon_i), i = 1\dots I$.

6. Calculate number of points in each interval to be generated:

$$N_i = f_i N, \text{ where } N \text{ is the total number of generated data points.}$$

7. Generate N_i values in interval $[\epsilon_i - \Delta\epsilon/2, \epsilon_i + \Delta\epsilon/2]$ by using standard built in computer random number generator: $\epsilon_k^{(i)} = \text{random}(0\dots\Delta\epsilon) + (\epsilon_i - \Delta\epsilon/2), k=1\dots N_i, i=1\dots I$. After this the following vector is formed: $\epsilon_l = \{\epsilon_1^{(1)} \dots \epsilon_{N_1}^{(1)}, \epsilon_1^{(2)} \dots \epsilon_{N_2}^{(2)}, \dots, \epsilon_1^{(I)} \dots \epsilon_{N_I}^{(I)}\}$.

8. Again standard random generator is used to pick M values from vector ϵ_l , where l is randomly generated: $l = \text{random}(1 \dots N)$.

Specimen consisting of M segments that have strength distributed according to Weibull distribution is obtained. Length of this specimen is linked with the size of the segment. For example segment size can be chosen as $l_{seg} = 0.1b$, then specimen length is: $L = 0.1bM$.

Weibull distribution that is obtained for cracking strain is later converted to cracking stress by: $\sigma_T^u = E_2 \epsilon_T^u$.

Monte-Carlo simulation of the transverse cracking

Displacement controlled experiment is assumed. Applied strain is increasing stepwise with an increment of $\Delta \epsilon_x$. After each step stress σ_i in every segment of 90^0 layer is calculated according to Eqn. 5. This calculated stress is compared with strength of each segment and if $\sigma_i > \sigma_{Ti}^u$ then i -th segment is failed and new crack is introduced in the middle of the segment. This procedure is continued until defined crack density is reached or maximum allowed strain ϵ_x^{\max} is exceeded.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Unidirectional GF/EP laminates were tested in order to obtain elastic constants of unidirectional composite. The results are following: $E_1 = 44.73$ GPa, $E_2 = 12.76$ GPa, $G_{12} = 5.80$ GPa, $\nu_{12} = 0.297$. Data that were not available from the test were taken for similar material composition: $G_{23} = 4.49$ GPa, $\nu_{23} = 0.42$.

Approach used to predict stiffness reduction in $[\pm\theta, 90_4]_s$ $\theta = 0, 15, 30, 40$ GF/EP laminate for a given crack density was verified in another study [3]. Results of experiment and prediction for cross-ply laminates are shown in Fig. 2a,b.

Fig. 2: Stiffness and Poisson ratio reduction due to transverse cracking.

In order to predict stiffness reduction as a function of applied strain, damage evolution should be estimated from experiment or by computer simulation. Computer simulation based on approach described earlier requires Weibull parameters for strength distribution in 90^0 layer. These parameters can be obtained from fitting data from simulation to experimental data. Fitting is performed using Hashin's model to calculate stress distribution and results are presented in Fig. 3. It gives following parameters: $\alpha = 9$, $\beta = 1.4\%$ (cracking strain). These values are in the range of ones shown for GF/EP in other studies [4,5]. Simulation was done

with following parameters: $N = 3 \cdot 10^4$, $M = 2 \cdot 10^3$, $l_{seg} = 2.5 \cdot 10^{-5}$ m \Rightarrow $L = 5 \cdot 10^{-2}$ m. Combining Fig. 3 and Fig. 2a,b stiffness reduction as a function of applied strain is obtained.

Fig. 3: Crack Density as a function of applied strain; experiment and simulation.

Fig. 4: Stiffness and Poisson's ratio reduction as a function of applied strain.

Fig. 5: Crack evolution obtained by using different models to calculate stress distribution.

The results are shown in Fig. 4a,b. It is clear that stress distribution calculation method influences accuracy of prediction. This is true not only for prediction of stiffness and Poisson's ratio reduction but also for damage evolution simulation.

The same models as in prediction of property reduction are used in computer simulation in order to compare them. These results are shown in Fig. 5. It should be noted that these simulations are done for the same strength distribution in 90^0 layer. Results in Fig. 5 show that when stresses are calculated by using original shear lag model (Sh.L-1) computer simulation does not give satisfactory results. Modification of shear lag model (Sh.L-2) slightly underestimated prediction in this strain region but is much closer to the experiment than Sh.L-1 model. Hashin's models of course gives the best fit since it was used to obtain Weibull parameters by fitting procedure. Farther we use only Sh.L-2 and Hashin's models.

The next step is to predict damage evolution in laminates with other than $[0_2, 90_4]_s$ lay-up by using the same Weibull parameters obtained from experimental results for cross-ply laminates. In Fig.6a experimental data for damage evolution in laminates with different lay-up are compared. Only linear approximations of experimental data are shown in order to clarify picture for comparison (for more details see [3]). These data show that actually damage evolution is not that different for different lay-ups, except one for $[\pm 40, 90_4]_s$ laminate. In Fig.6b,c results of simulation are shown. These calculations are performed with the same M, l_{seg}, N as before and strength distribution for 90^0 layer is the same for all cases.

Fig. 6: Crack density as a function of applied strain: different lay-ups of laminate.

Results obtained by computer simulation show that damage evolution for all lay-ups differs very small, including $[\pm 40, 90_4]_s$ laminate. It can be explain by small difference in stresses in 90^0 layer predicted by used models. In general it correlates rather well with experimental results except laminate with ± 40 as an outer layer. This is because used models don't take into account damage in outer layer, which is the case for $[\pm 40, 90_4]_s$ laminate [3].

Results of computer simulation of damage evolution can be slightly different from each other even for the same laminate lay-up since new strength distribution in 90^0 layer is generated during every run of simulation. In order to average these data, five runs of simulation are performed for each lay-up by using two models, modified shear lag (Sh.L.-2) and Hashin's. Then these data are approximated by polynomial function and obtained ρ - ϵ relationship is used to present changes of elastic constants of laminate as a function of applied strain. Prediction of the properties of laminate as a function of crack density obtained in [3] is used in this procedure. Results of it are presented in Fig. 7-9.

Fig. 7: Stiffness and Poisson's ratio reduction as a function of ϵ_x , $[\pm 15, 90_4]_s$ laminate.

Fig. 8: Stiffness and Poisson's ratio reduction as a function of ϵ_x , $[\pm 30, 90_4]_s$ laminate.

In these simulations the same model was used to predict damage evolution and stiffness reduction. Both used models give fairly good agreement with experiment, even in case of $[\pm 40, 90_4]_s$ laminate, therefore it is difficult to choose any preferable model. Probably Sh.L.-2 looks better than Hashin's in some cases.

Fig. 9: Stiffness and Poisson's ratio reduction as a function of ϵ_x , $[\pm 40, 90_4]_s$ laminate.

CONCLUSIONS

Weibull strength distribution in 90° layer is assumed, strength approach and Monte-Carlo simulation is used to model damage evolution in 90° layer. Crack density as a function of applied strain is obtained. Weibull parameters are determined from experimental data for $[0_2, 90_4]_s$ laminate and then used for other lay-ups. Stiffness reduction in $[S, 90_n]_s$ symmetric laminates, containing orthotropic sub-laminates (S) is analyzed as a function of crack density in 90° layer. It is recalculated as a function of applied strain by using damage evolution from computer simulation.

Modification of shear lag model and Hashin's model are used for calculations of stress distribution in cracked middle layer in damage evolution simulation. Both of these models show fairly good agreement with experimental data for damage evolution. Nevertheless, Hashin's model gives results closer to experiment. The same models are also used to predict stiffness reduction in $[S, 90_n]_s$ laminates. In this case models predict stiffness and Poisson's ratio reduction as a function of applied strain with satisfactory accuracy. Shear lag model gives slightly better results than Hashin's.

This study shows that it is possible to predict damage evolution in other than cross-ply laminates with fairly good accuracy by using Monte-Carlo computer simulation. Weibull parameters for 90° layer can be obtained from experimental data for $[0_2, 90_4]_s$ laminates and then used for laminates with $[S, 90_n]_s$ lay-ups that contain the same middle layer.

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APPENDIX

A1. Shear Lag model

$$\psi(\bar{x}) = \frac{\cosh(\xi \bar{x})}{\cosh(\xi \bar{l}_0)}, \quad R(\bar{l}_0) = \int_{-\bar{l}_0}^{+\bar{l}_0} \psi(\bar{x}) d\bar{x} = \frac{2}{\xi} \tanh(\xi \bar{l}_0), \quad \text{where} \quad \xi^2 = \bar{G} \frac{d(E_2 + b E_x^s)}{b E_2 E_x^s}$$

Sh.L.-1: $\bar{G} = G_m / d_0$, G_m - shear modulus of matrix, d_0 - thickness of the resin rich region.

Sh.L.-2: $\bar{G} = G_{23} / d$, G_{23} - out of plane shear modulus, d - half of thickness of the 90°-layer.

A2. Hashin's model

$\psi(\bar{x}) = A_1 \cosh(\alpha \bar{x}) \cos(\beta \bar{x}) + A_2 \sinh(\alpha \bar{x}) \sin(\beta \bar{x})$, A_1, A_2 : from zero stress boundary conditions.

$$R(\bar{l}_0) = \frac{4\alpha\beta}{\alpha^2 + \beta^2} \frac{\cosh(2\alpha \bar{l}_0) - \cos(2\beta \bar{l}_0)}{\beta \sinh(2\alpha \bar{l}_0) + \alpha \sin(2\beta \bar{l}_0)}, \quad \alpha = q^{1/4} \cos \frac{\theta}{2}, \quad \beta = q^{1/4} \sin \frac{\theta}{2}, \quad \tan \theta = \sqrt{\frac{4q}{p^2} - 1}$$

$$p = \frac{C_{02} - C_{11}}{C_{22}}, \quad q = \frac{C_{00}}{C_{22}}, \quad C_{00} = \frac{1}{E_2} + \frac{1}{E_x^s} \frac{1}{\bar{b}}, \quad C_{02} = \frac{\nu_{23}}{E_2} \left(\bar{b} + \frac{2}{3} \right) - \frac{\nu_{xz}^s}{3E_x^s} \bar{b}, \quad C_{11} = \frac{1}{3G_{23}} + \frac{1}{3G_{xz}^s} \bar{b}$$

$$C_{22} = \frac{1}{E_2} \left(\frac{1}{4} \bar{b}^2 + \frac{1}{3} \bar{b} + \frac{8}{60} \right) + \frac{1}{20E_z^s} \bar{b}^3$$

A3. Used notations

$E_1, E_2, G_{12}, G_{23}, \nu_{12}, \nu_{21}, \nu_{23}$:	elastic constants of unidirectional ply;
$E_x^s, E_z^s, G_{xz}^s, \nu_{xy}^s, \nu_{xz}^s$:	elastic constants of the sub-laminate;
$E_{x0}, \nu_{xy0}, E_x, \nu_{xy}$:	Young's modulus and Poisson's ratio of the intact (0) and cracked laminate;
S_{ij}, S_{ij}^s :	compliance matrices of the unidirectional ply and sub-laminate (s).